

BIBLIOMETRIC STUDY OF THE JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC LIBRARIANSHIP 2016-2020

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ABSTRACT

The Journal of Academic Librarianship is a peer-reviewed academic journal that covers a wide range of topics related to academic libraries. It publishes book reviews, analytical articles, and bibliographic essays. Established in 1975, it is published by Elsevier. The journal has been a bimonthly publication since its inception in March 1975. The initial editors were Richard M. Dougherty and William H. Webb, and the current editor-in-chief is Amanda Folk from Ohio State University. A study analyzed the publication trends, authorship patterns, collaboration rates, and article length in the 'Journal of Academic Librarianship' (JAL) from 2016 to 2020. A total of 376 articles from databases like Web of Science, Science Direct, and Citation Database were examined. In 2020, 86 articles (22.87%) were published, the highest in the study period. Single-authored articles accounted for 37.23% (140 articles), with the most articles in Issue No. 4 (73). The collaboration rate peaked in 2016 at 0.69, averaging 0.62 over the five years. The journal has an Impact Factor of 2.5 and is indexed in Scopus and the Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI), with Mendeley linked datasets. The study also tested hypotheses on research gaps, and all gold open access articles are freely accessible for everyone.

Keywords: Bibliometric Study, Authorship Pattern, and Academic Librarianship

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INTRODUCTION

Bibliometrics are valuable tools that can be utilized in the pre-award phase for various purposes. They can help document and support the researcher and research team's qualifications as partners or coordinators of a project. Often, CVs of the team members must be submitted along with publication lists and other bibliometric data such as H-index and Journal impact factor. Additionally, bibliometrics can aid in identifying key partners by surveying the most suitable contributors in the field. The term "bibliométric" was coined by Paul Otlet in 1934, referring to the measurement of all aspects related to the publication and reading of books and documents. The term "bibliometrics" was coined by Alan Pritchard in a 1969 paper titled "Statistical Bibliography or Bibliometrics?" where he defined it as the application of mathematics and statistical methods to books and other forms of communication. The Journal of Academic Librarianship is an international, refereed journal that publishes articles focusing on problems and issues relevant to college and university libraries. JAL serves as a platform for authors to present research findings, practical applications, and significance, analyze policies, practices, issues, trends, and speculate about the future of academic librarianship. It also features analytical bibliographic essays and philosophical treatises. Each issue of JAL includes special features such as information on academic library technology issues, research in international librarianship, and digests of special reports. The journal is published by Science Direct and has been in publication since 1975, with 42 volumes to date. It is a bimonthly publication that includes book reviews, analytical articles, and bibliographic essays focusing on issues related to college and university libraries.

METHODS

The study selected the Journal of Academic Librarianship (JAL) as the primary source for the period 2016-2020. The search strategy used in the 'Science Direct' citation database involved collecting data from a total of 376 articles. This included information on the number of contributions, authors, references, and the length of pages to align with the study objectives.

OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of the study are to analyze the articles and their citations to assess the Journal of Academic Librarianship from 2016 to 2020.

1. Analyze the distribution of articles by issue and year, as well as the authorship pattern.
2. Evaluate the distribution of publications based on citations.
3. Investigate collaboration levels and identify top authors in terms of productivity.
4. Determine the article length and geographical distribution.
5. Identify institutions that make significant contributions to the field.

RESULTS

The results are presented based on different criteria and are further elaborated in the tables below:

Table 1: Year Wise Publications

Year	Volume No.	Issue No.	Articles	%
2016	42	6	84	22.34
2017	43	6	67	17.82
2018	44	6	64	17.02
2019	45	6	75	19.95
2020	46	6	86	22.87
Total			376	100

Table 1 shows the distribution of 376 articles published in JAL from 2016 to 2020. The highest number of articles were published in 2020 (86, 22.87%), followed by 2016 (84, 22.34%) and 2019 (75, 19.95%). The lowest number of articles were published in 2018 (64, 17.02%) during the study period.

Table 2: Distribution of Articles by Issue

Year	Vol. No	Issue No						Total
		1	2	3	4	5	6	
2016	42	13	10	10	19	17	15	84
2017	43	12	9	11	13	11	11	67
2018	44	9	11	10	14	9	11	64
2019	45	10	14	13	10	16	12	75
2020	46	15	9	16	17	13	16	86
Total		59	53	60	73	66	65	376

Table 2 displays the distribution of articles in the JAL by issue. The highest number of articles were published in issue no. 4 (73), followed by issues no. 5 (66), 6 (65), and 3 (60). The lowest numbers of articles were in issues no. 1 and 2 (59, 53). This data is based on articles published in the JAL from 2016 to 2020.

Table 3: Authorship Patterns of Articles

Year	Single	Two	Three	Four	Five >	Total
2016	26	29	16	6	7	84
2017	29	22	11	3	2	67
2018	27	19	8	7	3	64
2019	26	16	14	17	2	75
2020	32	19	13	18	4	86
Total	140	105	62	51	18	376

Table 3 illustrates the authorship pattern of articles in JAL. The data reveals that the majority of articles were single-authored, accounting for 37.23% (140 articles). This was followed by articles with two authors at 27.92% (105 articles) and three authors at 16.48% (62 articles). Joint authorship of four authors accounted for 13.56% (51 articles), while joint authorship of five or more authors was the least common at 4.78% (18 articles) from 2016-2020.

To determine the degree of collaboration, the formula suggested by Subramanyam (1982) was used: Degree of collaboration $DC = N_m / (N_m + N_s)$

Where: DC = Degree of collaboration

N_m = Number of multiple authors

N_s = Number of single authors

Table 4: Degree of Collaboration Year Wise

Year	Single-Authored Papers (N _s)	Multiple-Authored Papers (N _m)	Degree of Collaboration (C)
2016	26	58	0.69
2017	29	38	0.57
2018	27	37	0.58
2019	26	49	0.65
2020	32	54	0.63
Total	140	236	0.63

Table 4 shows the trends in single and joint authorship in the JAL from 2016 to 2020. Collaboration levels have increased over the years, ranging from 0.57 to 0.69. The highest collaboration rate was in 2016 at 0.69, with an average collaboration rate of 0.62 during the study period.

Table 5: Articles Length

Pages	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	Total
1-5	10	13	9	21	34	87
6-10	55	41	38	43	38	215
11-15	19	11	14	8	9	61
16-20	--	2	3	3	5	13
Total	84	67	64	75	86	376

Table 5 shows the distribution of page lengths for articles in 60 issues and 656 articles published in JAL. The majority of articles (57.18%) were between 6-10 pages, with 215 articles falling into this category. Additionally, 23.13% (87 articles) were 1-5 pages long, 16.22% (61 articles) were 11-15 pages long, and 3.45% (13 articles) were 16-20 pages long in JAL from 2016 to 2020.

DISCUSSION

Research conducted by Richard B. Lamptey and Nelius Boshoff in 2020 focused on the academic environment for librarians at public universities in Ghana. The study aimed to understand how these librarians are able to meet their research and publication requirements. A web survey was conducted to assess the resources and opportunities available for research. Additionally, a bibliometric analysis of journal articles was carried out to examine the research output of academic librarians in Ghana, including their co-authorship patterns, publication preferences, and research visibility. The findings revealed that academic librarians tend to publish single-authored or institutionally co-authored articles in local journals. Their research visibility, as measured by citation scores in Google Scholar, was limited due to a lack of international collaboration. Participation in projects, funding opportunities, conference attendance, and publishing were often tied to having a research qualification. Despite challenges, some librarians were able to engage in research activities.

A bibliometric study was conducted on various journals in the field of Library and Information Science. Hydar Ali, Mahadevamurthy, and Jagadeesha (2015) analyzed publications in the Journal of Academic Librarianship from 1999 to 2016. They found that 47.81% of the publications were articles, with the highest number of publications in 1999. There was a sharp decrease in the growth rate from 1999 to 2007. The majority of documents (72.91%) were single-authored. The keywords "Academic libraries" and "Information Literacy" were frequently used, appearing in 30 and 27 publications, respectively.

Jayaprakash (2015) conducted a bibliometric analysis of 781 publications on cloud computing from 2000 to 2014 in journals published by Emerald Publications. The study revealed that single-author articles were the most common. The majority of literature on cloud computing was found in Library Hi Tech News and Library Hi Tech journals. Awasthi (2015) analyzed 261 articles published in the journal 'Library Trends' from 2008 to 2014. The study showed that the summer and winter issues had the highest number of published articles. Single authors contributed more than joint authors, and the majority of articles had a page length ranging from 11 to 21 pages.

Singh and Harish Chander (2014) analyzed 336 articles from the 'Library Management' journal published between 2006 and 2012. The top contributing countries were the USA, UK, Australia, China, India, and Canada. Most papers were authored by a single author (56.55%), followed by two authors (29.17%). Sudha Rani (2014) studied scholarly communications in 'PEARL: A Journal of Library and Information Science' from 2007 to 2012. The journal featured articles from India and other countries, with two-authored articles being the most common, followed by single and three-authored articles. The average collaboration rate was 0.61.

Roy and Basak (2013) analyzed research articles in the 'Journal of Documentation' from 2005 to 2010. They found that most papers were co-authored, with a collaboration degree of 0.51. The U.K. had the highest contribution, and the average citation per paper was 43. Satpathy et al. (2013) examined articles from the top ten open access journals in Library & Information Science indexed in the Scopus database in 2011. The majority of papers were authored by single authors, followed by two-authored and three-authored papers. Collaboration levels ranged from 0.33 to 0.8. The USA ranked highest in terms of country productivity.

CONCLUSION

The 'Journal of Academic Librarianship' is a leading international academic journal in Library and Information Science. In 2020, it published 86 articles (22.87%) on academic librarianship topics such as information literacy, higher education libraries, e-resources, information seeking, user studies and faculty issues. Authors who publish with us receive benefits including free PDFs, a flexible copyright policy and exclusive discounts on Elsevier publications. This subject area covers education, library & information sciences, with a Cite Score of 5.3 and an Impact Factor of 2.5. Abstracting and Indexing services are available through Scopus and the Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI), with linked datasets associated with Mendeley. All articles published in gold open access are freely available for everyone to read, download, copy, and distribute. This journal offers Creative Commons Attribution licenses and DOI services that specify how the articles can be reused.

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